

Creation of tools and materials for composition from data and metadata

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of *PyComposition* is to use data and metadata to create, based on them, a musical composition system consisting of musical materials, and compositional tools. The creation of this system will be determined by the characteristics of a given set of data.

In every musical system there is a system of hierarchy that relates the different constituent notes. In the case of tonal music, the hierarchy is based on a base note, called the tonic, and on a series of levels of greater or lesser proximity to this note that generate different degrees of tension in relation to it. In *PyComposition*, the objective is to base the structure of a musical composition on other base reference, the data.

In the example that will be presented throughout this article, a database from a weather station will be used. The data will be processed to determine which are the characteristics to be employed in order to build the musical system. This will be done in the *Python* environment, with the help of external libraries. Once the system is built, a sample score will be produced thanks to the *music21* library.

The process we will refer to, in which a series of data is used to generate a musical discourse, will be called *musification* [3], differentiating it from *sonification* [5], the result of which is sound synthesis. A given set of data is mapped to a given set of musical parameters to be encoded into a musical notation system. The framework of this work is computer-aided algorithmic music composition[1].

1. INTRODUCTION

PyComposition serves as a model to operate as an alternative to other environments and computer-assisted composition tools that are developed in purely graphical environments that work with objects, as is the case of *Max Msp*¹, *Pure Data*² or *Open Music*³, when dealing with the musification of data. *Python* offers us the possibility of clearly documenting the procedures performed, and speeding up the list processing. The code describes the genesis of a piece,

¹<https://cycling74.com/>

²<https://puredata.info/>

³<https://openmusic-project.github.io/>

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Web Audio Conference WAC-2022, December 6–8, 2022, Cannes, France.

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that can afterwards be modified or extended according to each composition. It shows basic operations to be used in the treatment of lists, operations that will be link to basic compositional procedures used in the treatment of musical material.

These composition techniques consist of : the establishment of polar notes that will play the role of the previously mentioned tonic, the construction of harmonies from the unfolding of melodies, correlating the vertical and horizontal axes in the deployment of the musical discourse, the transposition of a musical material according to the different established polar notes, the interrelation of the parameters of pitch and duration established from the same numerical values, the inversion and retrogradation of a musical material, the generation of melodies from the same group of notes considered as a *pitch class set*⁴.

After the explanations about the synthesis of the musical materials and the composition tools of *PyComposition*, an evaluation will be made about the interpretative aspect of this type of algorithmic compositions, for the case of electronic devices and for the case of acoustic instruments. When it comes to tonal music, where the basis of the musical language is tonal sound, the music is played mostly by acoustic instruments with the ability to produce tones, except for percussion instruments without defined intonation. There is a correspondence and resonance between language and the performing instrument. During the 20th century with musical styles such as the "Klang Komposition" developed by Helmut Lachenman⁵ (influenced by the *musique concrète* of Pierre Schaeffer), where the sound palette integrates all the noises that were normally left out of the sound repertoire to be used, the sound possibilities are expanded, forcing the instruments to use extended techniques. Through *musification* the sense of expansion is different, it consists in using other dynamic forms⁶ and other harmonic systems than those suggested by the tonal system, where the relationship between the components of a sound are proportionally related to a tonic. Therefore, the musicians are pushed to play other types of pitch systems, and other dynamic forms than the succession of tensions and distensions with respect to a center.

⁴More information about *pitch class sets* can be found in Chapman, A. (1981). Some Intervallic Aspects of Pitch-Class Set Relations. *Journal of Music Theory*, 25(2), 275–290.[2]

⁵<https://brahms.ircam.fr/fr/helmut-lachenmann>

⁶What D. Stern calls the *forms of vitality* [4]

2. ANALYTIC, TRANSFORMATIONAL AND GENERATIVE

In composition, music materials used, can be a sequence of four notes like the beginning of Beethoven's 5th, what we call a "motive", or for exemple a long theme like the one of the funeral march of the third movement of Mahler's Titan symphony. Then a series of procedures that together constitute a certain technique allow us to vary this initial material. The musical discourse will be created by combining this initial material and its various variants, to generally return at the end of the "path" (the piece) to the initial material. At least this is the general plan in tonal music, where the point of departure and arrival is the tonic and the theme in its original form, and the points of variation are the neighboring tonalities as well as the theme/motive in all its variations, stretched, compressed, fragmented, etc.

These terms "analytic", "transformational" and "generative" refer to a classification of processes introduced in the context of algorithmic music composition[6]. Analytical process types will be characterized by reducing the amount of data by extracting only certain characteristics. An example might be to extract the scale of a melody. Transformational processes do not necessarily alter the amount of data. An example of this procedure is the transposition of a musical passage to another key. Generative processes tend to increase the amount of data. An example would be the generation of chords from a single note. These three types of processes will be developed in the next subsections which will detail the procedures and tools used for musical composition in Pycomposition. In some cases we will work with data in numerical form, and in others with the musical notation resulting from the mapping between data and musical parameters. This allows the composer to make intermediate compositional decisions, based on the partial musical results.

In the case of a composer, this decisions are gonna be guided by his/her artistic interest plus the musical background education. In most of the cases the sonification performed by a scientist, "sounds bad" for a musician, just because there is no artistic intention or interest put on it. Or a musical training to guide the decisions. On the other hand, the sonification or the musification made by a musician who is going to be guided only by his/her musicality, probably does not serve the scientist at all. The composer will tend to follow the model of the data, as well as to vary it when the ear demands it.

As far as the musical relevance is concerned, the interesting thing about using data to generate compositional materials or a composition itself, is that this set of data has a logic in itself, a structure, different from that of sound, which can then be transposed into a musical language. It is an opportunity to discover new musical logics in this use of data. Everything we can digitize is a potential model to generate a compositional system, the possibilities that open up to composition are endless. Then it is left to judge what does or does not contain a musical interest.

By looking at a list of numbers we should be able to anticipate their potential musical interest. If we take into account the analytical processes described above, we should be able to anticipate what kind of language we can synthesize from this set of numbers, and what kind of musical style and instrumentation might be suitable. Then we must be able to imagine what kind of variations suit this set of

numbers/notes and thirdly we must be able to imagine what principles we can apply to proliferate the materials by generating more elements from the available ones.

To cite a few examples, repetitive material may suit an accompaniment, but not so much a main melody, unless we want to compose a piece in a minimalist style, for example. This not being the case, it will be convenient to make different transpositions and variations of this material to create some kind of interest. A continuously varying musical material can be used for a melody, although it will have to be fragmented and limited to a certain register if it is to be played by an acoustic instrument. Numbers already allow us to imagine these aspects, even though the visualization of a score keeps on being much more significant for a composer.

2.1 Analytic processes and metadata

The metadata will facilitate the analytical process of the data and allow us to group the musical materials according to their characteristics. A meteorological database corresponding to the city of Buenos Aires, with a humid subtropical climate and four seasons, will not be much like a database for the city of Quito with an equatorial climate and only dry and humid weather. Their variation's "rythm" is different. The category of meteorological data will describe a certain body of data, which will have certain characteristics in common, such as the correspondence to time lapses as a common reference, a shared measurement system, but which will differ greatly in their content according to the geographical position of the analyzed sites. For trimestral temperature measurements, there will be no major changes in the case of an equatorial climate as opposed to a humid subtropical climate with four marked seasons.

Likewise, the flow of data concerning an electrocardiogram will not resemble the positional data of a bee with respect to a flower. The characteristics of the type of variation of this data stream allow us to anticipate the dynamic form that this data will give to the musical parameter to which it is linked. In the first case, we can imagine a regular movement with slight variations, which would be of little interest for a melody but could establish a rhythmic pulse on which to unfold a composition, or establish the dynamic curve of intensity of the music. In the second case, the position in space of the bee will follow irregular trajectories, with probably points of rest on the flower. This movement will occur repeatedly, not always being the same each time, but probably maintaining the point of rest on the flower. We can imagine in this case, that the data flow of the bee's position is interesting as a melody. This kind of speculations that we can make from the description of the type of data, can be further evaluated thanks to the sonification and musification of partial stages in the production of materials. This allows us to gradually shape the composition. In the presented *PyComposition* model we have chosen to assign the same data set values to the duration and pitch of notes. Higher pitched sounds will last longer and lower pitched sounds will be shorter, the opposite of what happens acoustically. We will leave articulation, timbre and intensity aside in this example. In principle for an aesthetic decision to avoid as a sound result a texture of points and lines as in Oliver Messiaen's "Mode de valeurs et d'intensités"⁷ where there was a list of pitches, intensities, durations, articulations, and in-

⁷<https://brahms.ircam.fr/fr/works/work/10603/>

tensities assigned. To avoid this resulting sound texture that gives the impression of randomness, a succession of dots and lines in the style of Kandinsky, just pitch and duration will be assigned. Once the pitches and durations are assigned, we will analyze the totality of the notes by sections. As we would do in any music composition.⁸ The procedure then will be to extract from each section, the notes used, without repetition, to deduce the scales. Afterwards, we can analyze in the totality of the set, which are the notes that are repeated more. These will be the "poles" of attraction, what in tonal music where the "tonics". A recurrent procedure to which Beethoven used to resort to establish a tonal center, was to repeat a note. Here, we will do the same but in the inverse sense, to deduce the centers of attraction. Let us imagine that these values correspond, in order of greater to lesser preponderance (amount of repetitions), DO4, MI4, FA4, SOL4, SIb4. We will then calculate the distance between the main center, DO, and each of the other notes, now being the "poles". This resulting distance will correspond to a musical interval. In the example they are, in semitones: of 4, 5, 7 and 10 semitones. These intervals will determine the main transpositions. What in a tonal context we would call modulations, the transits through neighboring tonalities, in this case are the transpositions to the different "poles" of attraction of our set.

2.2 Transformational processes and level of variability

The transposition is a transformational procedure, which will consist in *Python* of adding or subtracting a numerical value (that of the musical interval mentioned) to each of the elements of the set, in the list of pitches. Other types of transformational procedures may concern those that deal with the order of the elements of the set of values. In composition this type of techniques can be found among the serialist techniques, where an original series, an inverted series, a retrograde series and an inverted retrograde series were used. But we also find these procedures in which the order of the elements of a musical material is altered further back in the history of music. We can cite as an example the two-part canon *Cancrizans* by J. S. Bach⁹ In this composition the lower voice acts as a retrogradation of the upper voice, and in the middle of the piece both voices meet facing a mirror between the two parts. We will use the retrogradation, which in the case of the list, will simply consist in inverting the order of the elements. Moreover, reordering of the elements will be used in the generation of melodies. Given a certain scale, which contains in itself, given the intervals between the different notes, a certain harmonic color, we will generate melodies combining randomly this group of notes, with values coming from the data set of durations.

The same procedures were performed on four groups of data. All four coming from the same meteorological database. Each one contains a different combination of meteorological parameters (temperature, atmospheric pressure, humidity, wind speed, wind deg, sky cover) and corresponds

⁸In general the same harmony is maintained through a certain passage. The rhythm of the harmony varies greatly throughout history. In the 18th century an average would be two different chords for each bar, and in the 20th century we can find an entire work written on a single harmony or even a single note.

⁹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Crab_canon

to different time periods (data per hour, per day, per week, per month, per quarter, per semester, per year, etc.). The most interesting results achieved corresponded to the version using a single parameter over different time scales. In the case of the combination of different parameters, the mix of parameters that vary similarly in terms of magnitude and frequency worked also favorably. When all the parameters chosen performed very differently, the result was a pattern that repeated itself each time in a varied manner, rather than being perceived as a single continuous entity. So in the case of listening to the evolution of five parameters, we hear a pattern of five notes, with some notes that are almost unchanged and one or two that are modified. Through experimentation we can infer different types of musical textures from the data set and the mappings we use, the main feature to take into account, music being an art of time, is the level of variability of the values over time.

2.3 Generative harmonies

The idea behind the generation of melodies and chords in the *PyComposition* example model, as already mentioned, is that while maintaining the same harmonic color, contained by this set of notes that form a "harmonic field", to produce different samples of melodies and chords as many possible combinations as we can make. The order of the components is changed, and at the same time new data is generated. The harmonic field concentrates the sound characteristics of scales and chords, regardless their disposition in the register.

In both cases, for melodies and chords, the elements to be used are chosen from the list of pitch values precisising the value of their position in the scale. In the case of chords, the experimentation has been limited to the use of triads, being possible to explore chords with a larger number of notes, and displayed in a wide register, which will confer other acoustic properties.

In what follows we will describe in detail and as clearly as possible the generation of musical materials, the methods employed, the process of score creation, the results, the application to the realization of a piece of music, and a conclusion of the completeness of the experiment.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In a first step, data is extracted from the Internet to generate the *json* file. In a second stage, different processes are applied to this dataset to create music materials. In a third instance, the different elements are combined to compose a music score.

3.1 Data collection

The data used in the example that we are going to describe, has been extracted from the site *Openweathermap*¹⁰. This by means of an API call specifying the latitude and longitude information corresponding to the city, and afterwards saving the data in *json* format.¹¹ The resulting json file in this case is named "datanice.json".

The meteorological mesearuments parsed for the pur-

¹⁰<https://home.openweathermap.org/>

¹¹See the "niceWeather_jsonFile" file located in the Github repository <https://github.com/RominaSR/PyComposition21> for more details.

pose of *PyComposition* example correspond to temperature (*temp*), unit - by default: Kelvin, metric: Celsius, imperial: Fahrenheit; humidity (*humidity*), percentage; wind gust (*wind_gust*), unit - by default: meter/sec, metric: meter/sec, imperial: miles/hour; dew point (*dew_point*), units - by default: Kelvin, metric: Celsius, imperial: Fahrenheit; wind direction (*wind_deg*), degrees (meteorological); UV index (*uvi*)¹².

3.2 Generation of musical materials

3.2.1 Mapping and scaling

A list is created in which the values of these meteorological measures are succeeded for each hour. This list will be scaled in two different ways, resulting in two different lists, one corresponding to the pitches of the notes, and the other corresponding to the durations. The same proportions are kept, but the scale is expanded to convene in the case of the pitches, with a central register, and in the case of the durations to fix a maximum of three whole note figures (the equivalent of twelve quarter notes).

For pitches, the scale goes from 36 to 72 (MIDI values corresponding to DO2 and DO5) and for durations from 0 to 12. The resulting values are rounded to one decimal place for pitches, and to three decimal places for note durations. The first ones are approximated to multiples of 0.50, which corresponds to the value of a quarter tone, and the second ones are approximated to multiples of 0.125, which corresponds to the value of a triple eighth note. Notes outside the range between C2 and C5 are then transposed to the closer octave so to enter into this range.

3.2.2 Original and retrograde scores

From this two lists, of pitches and durations, a first score is generated, which we call the "original score". Each note is printed with its corresponding pitch value to corroborate the mapping and see the correlation between the value and the display of the note in the score. Afterwards the two lists are inverted, generating a "retrograde score". Both generated scores are exported in *.mid* and *.xml* format, easily usable by music notation and production softwares. Once the two generation processes of these two scores are completed, a series of analyses are performed using the analytic tools of *music21*. Among these, it counts with the possibility of analyzing the distribution of notes by number of bars, the relationship between the pitch and duration of each note, the number of notes per octave, etc.

3.2.3 Scales, poles and transpositions

In order to extract scales, the original score file is parsed to get all the pitch values, to place them in the central octave of C4 and to remove the note repetitions. In this way, a scale including the whole "harmonic field" of the original score is obtained. The number of values of the score is then divided into six parts (named from "A" to "F"), and a scale is extracted from each of these sections.

In order to plan the transpositions of the "original score" onto another "harmonic fields", we look for "poles". The "poles" will be determined by calculating the most repeated note values in the set. The number of times each pitch and duration appears is counted and the five most repeated

Figure 1: Example of a chord

Figure 2: Example of a melody

elements of each category is determined. The five intervals of transposition are calculated subtracting each one of the five most repeated pitches to the value of the first note of the set.

3.2.4 Chords and melodies

A tool is created to generate melodies and chords from a set of pitches, the "harmonic field" of each subsection, which will give a certain harmonic color to these melodies, and a global set of durations, the initially constructed array. The chords and melodies corresponding to each of the six sections are then generated (Figures 1 and 2). In the case of chords, pitches are selected by determining the position in the scale, and they are randomly assigned durations from the initial set. In the case of melodies, different samples can be generated continuously by randomly selecting a pitch and duration for each note, from both the pitch and the duration sets. Keeping in this way the harmonic colour but changing the order of the notes, varying the melodic profile. For each fragment (A to F) we will then have one melody and two chords. The materials are in this case also generated in *xml* format, and can also be exported in midi format.

3.3 Score creation

Composing is essentially putting together different musical materials to make that combination become a whole, a musical work. After producing different materiales (melodies, chords, original and retrograde scores and transpositions), we plan how to organize them in time. For this example of *PyComposition* we imagined a simple tripartite form ABA'. In this ternary form, a first idea A is contrasted with a second one B, followed by the reappearance of the first one, variated. Part A uses the generated melodies and chords, and part B uses different transpositions of the first musification made directly from the *json* file.

Part A includes:

2x [melody D, quarter note rest, melody F, melody C], 2x [melody A], [quarter and sixteenth rests, melody D, melody F, melody C], [melody A, three quarter rests, eighth rest and thirty-second rest, melody E, chords E], 2x[melody A, three quarter rests, eighth rest and thirty-second rest, melody E, chords E], [chords A], eighth rest, 2x[chords F], [chords B], half rest, 2x[chords A]. See Figure 3.

Part B includes:

Transposition of [bars 0 to 2 of the retrograde score, melody A] to transposition interval 1, transposition of [bars 2 to 5 of the retrograde score, melody B] to transposition interval 1, transposition of [bars 6 to 7 of the retrograde score, melody C] to transposition interval 1, lower octave of [transposition of [melody D, melody F] to transposition

¹²<https://openweathermap.org/api/one-call-api>

Figure 3: Part A

interval 2, transposition of [melody C, melody A] to transposition interval 3, transposition of [melody E, melody B] to transposition interval 4], lower octave of [transposition of [chords E, A, F, C, and D] to interval 4], transposition of [bars 9-16 of original score] to transposition interval 4.

Part A' includes: Transposition of [bars 0 to 5 of Part A] to transposition interval 4, transposition of [bars 6 to 8 of Part A] to transposition interval 3, transposition of [bars 17 to 22 of Part A] to transposition interval 2, transposition to the upper octave of [transposition of [bars 45 to 50 of Part A] to transposition interval 1], whole rest, transposition to the upper octave of [bars 16 to 18 of Part A], [whole and half rest].

4. RESULTS

Below are some favorable results, and then some less favorable results of this *PyComposition* experience.

As for the favorable ones, we can point out the convenience of using *Python* as environment due to its efficiency in dealing with lists and long datasets. Moreover the possibility of documenting and modifying the structure of the code at any time is well adapted to the process of composing. Another aspect to point out is the usefulness of generative methods based on a few values, in order to palliate in *musicification* processes, data types that do not vary enormously in the chosen time lapse, as it is the case of our 24 hs dataset of the city of Nice. Another favorable aspect has been the possibility of using *music21* allowing the incorporation of a visual element in the form of a score that allows the composer to better follow the processes carried out. Finally, I would also like to point out the useful analysis tools available in this library. As an example we show the bar chart of *Figure 4*, showing the number of pitch classes.

As for the less favorable results, there are still some bugs in *music21*, such as in the rhythm constitution and it is not practical still to visualize microtones other than quarter tones (for which it is necessary to specify the values in

Figure 4: Number of pitch classes, *music21*

cents)¹³. We could also mention the *practicality* of using .xml file formats to connect different engraving softwares, what it is very useful, but at the same time *MusicXML* files are hardly readable correctly by the various music notation softwares available. In the case of *PyComposition* we recommend using *Musescore3*.

5. CONCLUSION

Data has become part of our daily life. Digitalization allows us to apprehend the surrounding world in a vast and at the same time always limited, unfinished, imperfect way. We would need an omnipresent digital system to be able to process all of the reality. Regarding the influence of it in our creative processes, we could agree that a person who looks at the colors of the sky to get inspired to write a piece of music is no different in essence from another person who takes a photo of the sky and seeks to translate the pixels of the photo into musical notes to make a composition. The essence of the creative act remains the same, the contemplation, the search for understanding, for expression. We tend to same the same things through different means.

The experimentation carried out with *PyComposition* shares the actual reflection on the place of these technologies in the daily life of a music composer. Although they can be compositional systems in themselves, there is a greater predisposition to be, as the title of this article says, materials and tools that serve the musical composition. Our ear has been trained for over 2000 years to hear and interpret music as well as the rest of our bodies to perform it in a certain system of musical structure. Integrating other forms of organization as it happened in some contemporary music of the XXth Century, it may take some time...but it is part of the evolution of our cultures. The proof is that other systems and dynamic forms in music exist in another cultures.

For future explorations we envision the incorporation of timbre, articulation and dynamics, the simplification of microtonal notation and the recognition of the "musical style" of the different data sets.

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